

ON PIN-LOADED HOLE WITH INTERFERENCE
IN A LAMINATED COMPOSITE

Kai-da Zhang
(Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xian, Shaanxi,
People's Republic of China)

and
Charles E.S. Ueng
(Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, Georgia 30332, USA)

ABSTRACT

A slightly larger pin, or a pin with interference is assumed in this paper. The purpose is to redistribute the stresses around the contact surface between the pin and the hole so the joint strength may be increased. A compact analytic solution for the stress distribution is obtained by the stress functions of complex variables. The stresses strongly depend on the contact angle. A threshold pin load is obtained which represents the maximum load possible in order to keep a full contact. Stresses along a characteristic curve are calculated and the failure strength is evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanically fastened joints are often used in laminated composites for transmitting the load from one structural component to another. However, a failure often occurs along the boundary of such holes. The study on how to fully understand the stress distribution and the possible failure modes around such a pin-loaded hole has become an interesting and important topic in the current research on composites for the purpose to improve the joint design.¹⁻⁴

In this paper, a slightly larger pin, or a pin with interference is assumed. The intention of such an interference is to redistribute the stresses around the contact area between the pin and the hole so the joint strength may be increased.

ANALYSIS

Extending the authors' earlier work¹, a compact analytic solution of the stress distribution around the contact area is obtained by the approach of stress functions of complex variables which satisfy the equilibrium equations and boundary conditions. A normalized interference parameter λ is introduced. A threshold of the pin load, P_{th} , is defined as the pin load which will change the problem from a full contact case to a partial contact case. Through the use of complex stress functions formed for this problem, a set of three equations are obtained, involving unknown parameters, namely, θ_0 , the contact angle, u_0 , the fastener displacement, c , a material parameter in a fairly complicated form, and P_{th}/P . A series of values of θ_0 is first assumed in order to solve for the remaining unknowns. The stresses are also evaluated along the characteristic curve under the condition that $P = 0$ but $\lambda \neq 0$ for the strength estimation purpose.

RESULTS

Certain sampling results are shown in Figs. 1 through 5. Due to space limitation, additional information will be provided during the presentation.

CONCLUSIONS

The compact analytic expressions obtained here appear to be reasonable and are potentially useful for the estimation of stresses in interference pin-loaded problems. The method simplifies greatly the computational work in comparing with other approaches. A suitable interference can raise the pin-load bearing strength and may increase the fatigue life of mechanically fastened joints.

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Fig. 1 Variation of P_{th}/P , $f_2(\theta_0)$ and c with θ_0 .

Fig. 2 Stress distribution around a hole in a $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate

Fig. 3 Stress distribution around a hole in a $[0/\pm 45_3/90]_s$ laminate

Fig. 4 Stress distribution around a hole in a $[0_8]_s$ laminate

Fig. 5 Stress distribution around a hole in a $[0_4/\pm 45/90_2]_s$ laminate